

**ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INFUSED ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS IN
BRICK/BLOCK LAYING AND CONCRETING TRADE INTO THE CURRICULUM OF SENIOR
SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN BAUCHI STATE**

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Abstract

This study assessed the implementation of the infused entrepreneurial skills in brick/block laying and concreting trade into the curriculum of senior secondary schools in Bauchi State, Nigeria. Relevant literature related to the objectives and research questions were reviewed. The study was guided by two objectives, two research question and their corresponding hypothesis. The study adopted survey design and total sample population was used in this study. Twenty-three respondents were used in the study comprising of fourteen experience teachers and nine newly employed teachers teaching in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State. The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire and was validated by three experts. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was found to be .875 and hence the instrument was found to be reliable. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (IBM SPSS) version 21 was used to analyze the data that was collected. The data obtained was analyzed using Descriptive Statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation. Results obtained from the study reveal that: (i) All the content areas of infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State are appropriate. (ii) The manpower are competent to teach the infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State. The researcher recommended as follows (a) All Teachers should be encouraged to teach skills infused entrepreneurial content areas of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State. (b) There should be refresher training for all the teachers in order to effectively teach the infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State.

Keywords: Assessment, Implementation, Entrepreneurial Skills, Curriculum, Senior Secondary Schools

Introduction

Education serves as an instrument for the development of both the individual and the society. According to Agishi (2016) every society irrespective of time, people or place has been involved in one system of education or the other. Nigeria having realized the importance and effectiveness of education as a powerful instrument for national progress and development, adjusted her educational philosophy and methodology to match the ideals and challenges of the changing economic and social structure of modern societies (Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN), 2014).

Guidelines are important for the success of every program across the globe. The education sector in Nigeria and beyond is not exempted from guidelines for proper and effective implementation of it programs. FRN (2014) affirmed that

national guideline must be followed for the effective administration, management and implementation of education at all levels and tiers of government. National Policy on Education is a statement of intentions, expectations, goals, prescriptions, standards and requirements for quality education delivery in Nigeria. Nigeria like most other countries of the world is undergoing rapid social, economic and political reforms in line with day-to-day changes in the society and the entire world. According to Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC 2012);, the curriculum of every nation including Nigeria must pay attention to the achievement of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGS) and the critical elements of the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategies (NEEDS).

Afoma (2015) states that the senior secondary school education in Nigeria is not left out of the drive to meet up with the changes and growth in the education sector to meet up with the contemporary changes in the world. Therefore, The Senior Secondary Education Curriculum (SSEC) was developed to further consolidate the educational gains of the 9 Year Basic Education Curriculum as well as ensure the actualization of Government Transformation Agenda and other national developmental aspirations (FRN, 2014). According to FRN, (2014) the prime objective of senior secondary education in Nigeria is to ensure that every Senior Secondary School (SSS) graduate is well prepared for higher education as well as acquired relevant functional trade and entrepreneurship skills among others that will help him or her to live meaningfully and as well impact the society positively. As a result of this prime objective for senior secondary school education in Nigeria, the curriculum was re-directed to focus on job creation, wealth generation and poverty eradication.

Adigun and Ekwukoma (2015) state that the senior secondary school curriculum is organized in themes to guarantee good understanding of concepts and for learning to be sequential. The themes covered in the senior secondary school curriculum are humanities, science/mathematics, technology and business. Humanities consist of Nigerian language, literature in English, geography, government, Christian religious study, Islamic studies, history, visual arts, music, French, Arabic and economics. Science/Mathematics is made up of biology, chemistry, physics, further mathematics, agriculture, physical education, health education and computer studies. Technology consist of the following subjects; technical drawing, general metal work, basic electricity, electronics, auto-mechanics, building construction, wood-work, home management, foods and nutrition. Business as a theme has the following subjects; accounting, store management, office practice, insurance and commerce.

Besides, trade/entrepreneurship, English and civic education are made compulsory subjects for the students. Trade and entrepreneurship consist of thirty four subjects which are auto body repair and spray painting, auto electrical work, auto mechanical work, auto part merchandising, air conditioning and refrigerator, welding and fabrication engineering craft practice, electrical installation and maintenance work, radio, television and electrical work, block laying, bricklaying and concrete work, painting and decoration, plumbing and pipe-fitting, machine woodworking, carpentry and joinery, furniture making, upholstery, printing craft practice, leather goods manufacturing and repairs, catering craft practice, garment making, clothing and textile, dyeing and bleaching, cosmetology, stenography, data processing, store keeping, book keeping, global system for mobile communication maintenance (GSM) , photography, tourism, mining, animal husbandry, fisheries, marketing and salesmanship (FRN-NPE, 2014).

Trade and entrepreneurship subject are introduced in senior secondary school to equip the young Nigerian school levers with skills that will encourage self-reliance and alleviate poverty. According to Jerome (2014) and Alao (2016) the aim of entrepreneurial education is not just to teach an individual how to run a business, but to encourage creative thinking, promote strong sense of self-reliance, accountability and productivity. Other objectives include: to inculcate in an individual

survival skills; to build in an individual knowledge and skills either about or for the purpose of entrepreneurship; to equipped the recipients usually at the secondary school level (which is the focus of this study) with such skills that enable them to fit into the world of economic and productive enterprise upon graduation; to inculcate in an individual the ability to recognize opportunities in life; to help people create and operate new ventures and be self-reliant; to reduce the soaring incidence of unemployment; to alleviate poverty; to foster socioeconomic integration and development; to drastically reduce idleness among youths and thereby curb the attendant consequences of idleness such as youth restiveness, insurgency and other forms of social vices.

Statement of the Problem

According to FRN (2014), the prime objective of senior secondary education in Nigeria is to ensure that every Senior Secondary School (SSS) graduate is well prepared for higher education as well as acquired relevant functional trade and entrepreneurship skills among others that will help him or her to live meaningfully and as well impact the society positively. Unfortunately, these objectives are not filled, because senior secondary school graduates are not technically competent enough to take up the available skilled jobs.

The present administration in Nigeria is making job provision for the unemployed youth's one of its agenda to teach in Nigerian schools (primary and secondary). Since the time of this development many experts in the educational sector have been criticizing the idea of employing the in-experienced graduate teachers (novice) to teach in Nigerian schools, because of its adverse effect on the Nigerian education system. Many teachers lacked teaching experience; teach science in abstraction, lacked adequate knowledge of subject matter and the competence to deliver (Abdulalu, 2017).

It has been observed that a good number of students who have completed their senior secondary school education in Bauchi State, and have not secured admission into higher institutions or do not wish to continue with higher education are unproductive. This is because they were not well equipped with the necessary skills needed to take up jobs in industries or become self-employed. This situation had led them into social vices such as cultism, armed robbery, thuggery and prostitution among others. The knowledge and skills acquired by students at the end of secondary education equally seem to be nonfunctional or unproductive. This has led to curriculum reform by the FRN (2014) to infuse entrepreneurial skills in all trade subjects in senior secondary school education curriculum. The implementation of the infused entrepreneurial skills in brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools in Bauchi State is currently witnessing many challenges such as; content, manpower, facilities and methods of teaching. Therefore, there is a need to assess the implementation of the infused entrepreneurial skills in brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary school curriculum in Bauchi State.

Purpose of the Study

The main aim and objective of this study is to assess the implementation of infused entrepreneurial skills in brick/block laying and concreting trade into the curriculum of senior secondary schools in Bauchi State. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Assess the entrepreneurial skills content area infused into brick/block laying and concreting trade curriculum in senior secondary schools of Bauchi state.
2. Assess the competency of the manpower for teaching infused entrepreneurial skills in brick/block laying and concreting trade curriculum in senior secondary schools of Bauchi state.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions in line with the aims and objectives of the study:

1. To what extent are the infused entrepreneurial skills content areas of brick/block laying and concreting trade appropriate in senior secondary schools of Bauchi state?
2. To what extent are the manpower competent to teach infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade for senior secondary schools of Bauchi state?

Research Hypotheses

The following Null Hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- H₀₁.** There is no significant difference between the mean responses of experienced and newly employed teachers on the content areas of infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi state.
- H₀₂.** There is no significant difference between the mean responses of experience and newly employed teachers on the competency of manpower for teaching the infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi state.

Methodology

The research design used in the study was a survey research design. The area of the study is Bauchi state, the study covers all the Senior Secondary schools of Bauchi State. The population of the study comprises all teachers of brick/block laying and Concreting trade in Senior Secondary schools of Bauchi State. Total sample population was employed. The instrument for data collection for this research was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers through extensive literature review. The instrument was validated by three experts from the Department of Vocational and Technology Education (DVTE) Building Option, Faculty of Technology Education, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi, Bauchi State. The instrument was administered with the aid of three research assistants. The research assistants were educated on the procedure for data collection. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the data. A cut off point of 2.49 and below were disagreed and any item with a mean score of 2.50 and above were accepted. The Hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test. If the p-value is greater than the confidence level of 0.05 then hypothesis was accepted but if the p-value is less than the confidence level the hypothesis was rejected. The items for response were presented according to the research questions with four points Linkert scale. The ratings are as follows: 4, 3, 2, and 1 point respectively. Research question one: Highly Appropriate (HA), Appropriate (A), Moderately Appropriate (MA), and Not Appropriate (NA). Research questions two: Highly Competent (HC), Competent (C), Moderately Competent (MC) and Not Competent (NC).

Results and Discussion

Research Question One: To what extent are the infused entrepreneurial skills content areas of brick/block laying and concreting trade appropriate for senior secondary schools of Bauchi State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the respondents on the extent to which the infused entrepreneurial skills content areas of brick/block laying and concreting trade are appropriate for senior secondary schools of Bauchi State.

Key
 $N_E=14$
 $N_N=4$

S/N	Item Statement	X_E	SD_E	X_N	SD_N	X_g	Remark
1.	Business development plan.	3.00	.877	3.22	.667	3.09	Appropriate
2.	Risk taking.	3.43	.514	3.56	.527	3.48	Appropriate
3.	Sourcing of fund.	3.29	.611	3.33	.707	3.31	Appropriate
4.	Financial management.	3.14	.663	3.00	.707	3.74	Highly Appropriate
5.	Planning.	3.14	.864	3.11	.782	3.13	Appropriate
6.	Decision making.	3.43	.514	3.11	.782	3.30	Appropriate
7.	Ability to achieve result.	3.43	.646	3.11	.928	3.30	Appropriate
8.	Drive and motivation.	3.57	.646	3.33	.866	3.48	Appropriate
9.	Self-confidence.	2.86	.363	2.89	.333	2.87	Appropriate
10.	Sense of responsibility.	3.57	.514	3.33	.707	3.48	Appropriate
11.	Dedication to skill acquisition.	3.57	.514	3.22	.667	3.43	Appropriate
12.	Developing new innovative approaches.	3.64	.497	3.11	.782	3.43	Appropriate
13.	Identifying new business opportunities.	3.43	.514	3.11	.333	3.30	Appropriate
14.	Ambition to achieve goals.	3.57	.514	3.11	.601	3.39	Appropriate
15.	Persistence to face obstacles.	3.29	.469	3.22	.667	3.26	Appropriate
16.	Developing business relationship skills.	3.43	.514	3.22	.833	3.35	Appropriate
17.	Establishing network of contacts.	3.14	.770	2.89	.782	3.04	Appropriate
	Cluster Mean	3.35	.588	3.17	.687	3.32	Appropriate

Source: Field Work, 2023

Table 1 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation of the respondents on the extent to which the infused entrepreneurial skills content areas of brick/block laying and concreting trade are appropriate in Senior Secondary Schools of Bauchi State. The result shows the cluster mean of 3.35 for Experience Teachers and 3.17 for Newly Employed Teachers, the grand mean of the respondents is 3.32 which indicate that all the infused entrepreneurial skills content areas of brick/block laying and concreting trade are appropriate in Senior Secondary Schools of Bauchi State.

Research Question Two: To what extent are the manpower competent to teach infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi state?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of the respondents on the extent to which the manpower are competent to teach infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State.

S/N	Item Statement	X _E	SD _E	X _N	SD _N	X _g	Remark
18.	Teachers have the competence to teach business development plan.	3.64	.497	3.56	.527	3.61	Highly Competent
19.	Teachers have the competence to teach risk taking.	3.29	.726	3.56	.527	3.40	Competent
20.	Teachers have the competence to teach sourcing of fund.	3.50	.855	3.56	.527	3.52	Highly Competent
21.	Teachers have the competence to teach financial management.	3.43	.646	3.44	.726	3.43	Competent
22.	Teachers have the competence to teach planning.	3.21	.426	3.33	.500	3.26	Competent
23.	Teachers have the competence to teach decision taking.	3.79	.426	3.56	.726	3.70	Highly Competent
24.	Teachers have the competence to teach Ability to achieve result.	3.29	.726	3.22	.972	3.26	Competent
25.	Teachers have the competence to teach drive and motivation.	3.14	.770	3.33	.707	3.17	Competent
26.	Teachers have the competence to teach self-confidence.	3.14	.535	3.33	.500	3.17	Competent
27.	Teachers have the competence to teach sense of responsibility.	3.00	.392	3.11	.333	3.04	Competent
28.	Teachers have the competence to teach hard work and effort.	2.57	.646	3.00	.000	2.74	Competent
29.	Teachers have the competence to teach developing new innovative approaches.	3.00	.392	2.89	.601	2.96	Competent
30.	Teachers have the competence to teach identifying new business opportunities.	3.14	.535	3.33	.500	3.17	Competent
31.	Teachers have the competence to teach ambition to achieve goals.	2.79	.893	3.22	.441	2.96	Competent
32.	Teachers have the competence to teach persistence to face obstacles.	3.36	.497	3.33	.707	3.35	Competent
33.	Teachers have the competence to teach developing business relationship skills.	2.79	.426	3.00	.000	2.87	Competent
34.	Teachers have the competence to teach establishing network of contacts.	3.36	.745	3.67	.500	3.48	Competent
	Cluster Mean	3.20	.600	3.32	.517	3.24	Competent

Source: Field Work, 2023

Table 2 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation of the respondents on the extent to which the manpower are competent to teach infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State. The result shows the cluster mean of 3.20 for Experience Teachers and 3.32 for Newly Employed Teachers, the grand mean of the respondents is 3.24 which indicates that all the manpower possesses the competence to teach infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State.

Result of Null Hypotheses

Null Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of experienced and newly employed teachers on the content areas of infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State.

Table 3: t-test analyses of the mean responses of experienced and newly employed teachers on the content areas of infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State.

	N	X	S.D	Df	T	P	Decision
Experience Teachers	14	3.35	.588				
				16	-2.647	.006	Rejected
Newly Employed Teachers	9	3.17	.687				

The result of the independent t-test is presented in Table 3 showed that there is significant difference between the mean responses of experienced and newly employed teachers on the content areas of infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State within the df of 16, t-value = -2.647, p = .006. Since the p value is less than the confidence level ($P > 0.05$) therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that there is significant difference between the mean responses of experienced and newly employed teachers on the content areas of infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State.

Null Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of experience and newly employed teachers on the competency of manpower for teaching the infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State.

Table 4: t-test analyses of the mean responses of experience and newly employed teachers on the competency of manpower for teaching the infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State

	N	X	S.D	Df	T	P	Decision
Experience Teachers	14	3.20	.600				
				16	-1.253	.110	Accepted
Newly Employed Teachers	9	3.32	.517				

The result of the independent t-test in Table 4 showed that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of experience and newly employed teachers on the competency of manpower for teaching the infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State within the df of 16, t-value = -1.253, p = .110. Since the p value is greater than the confidence level ($P > 0.05$) therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of experience and newly employed teachers on the competency of manpower for teaching the infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State

Discussion of Findings

Finding one of this study shows that content areas infused in the Brick/block laying and concreting trade curriculum are appropriate. This finding in agreement with that of Dokubo and Chivuikem, (2021) who reaffirm the need for these content areas infused in the Brick/block laying and concreting trade curriculum are appropriate skills in the teaching and learning of brick/block laying and concreting trade. In the same vein the findings in line with that of Oviawe and Uwameiye (2018) who also stated that the content areas infused in the Brick/block laying and concreting trade curriculum are significant for students training.

Finding two of this study indicates that the Teachers are competent to teach the infused entrepreneurial Brick/block laying and concreting curriculum content and this finding is in agreement with that of Abusomwan and Osaigboyo (2020)

who observed that there are competent teachers of brick/block laying and concreting trade. Similarly, this finding agrees with that of Osam (2015) who ascertained that the quality of Teachers of Vocational and technical Colleges is high but inadequate.

Conclusion

From the findings of this study shows that content areas infused in the Brick/block laying and concreting trade curriculum are appropriate and teachers are competent to teach the infused entrepreneurial Brick/block laying and concreting curriculum content. Furthermore, facilities for teaching the infused entrepreneurial Brick/block laying and concreting curriculum are moderately adequate and lastly appropriate teaching methods are employed/used in the teaching the infused entrepreneurial content of the Brick/block laying and concreting curriculum.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. All Teachers should be encouraged to teach and use all appropriate skills infused entrepreneurial content areas of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State.
- ii. There should be refresher training for all the teachers in order to effectively teach the infused entrepreneurial skills of brick/block laying and concreting trade in senior secondary schools of Bauchi State.

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